

Title: Iron Regulatory and Antioxidant Gene Variants Shape Biochemical Severity in β -Thalassemia

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Abstract

β -thalassemia is characterized by ineffective erythropoiesis, chronic transfusion dependence, and progressive iron overload. Dysregulated hepcidin signaling and oxidative stress contribute significantly to organ damage; however, genetic modifiers influencing iron metabolism and antioxidant defense remain incompletely defined. To evaluate biochemical alterations and investigate the association of HAMP rs10421768 and GSTP1 rs1695 SNPs with β -thalassemia susceptibility. A case–control study was conducted including β -thalassemia patients and healthy controls. Hepatic and renal biochemical parameters and serum ferritin were assessed. Genotyping of HAMP and GSTP1 SNP was performed using PCR-based methods. Genotype distributions were analyzed under multiple inheritance models. β -thalassemia patients demonstrated significantly elevated transaminases (SGOT and SGPT) and serum ferritin compared with controls, indicating hepatocellular injury and severe iron overload. Serum urea was modestly increased, while creatinine remained largely unchanged. GSTP1 rs1695 showed genotype-dependent association, with the strongest effect under the over-dominant model, whereas allelic association was not significant. In contrast, HAMP rs10421768 demonstrated significant association across dominant, recessive, and allelic models, with marked enrichment of the G allele among patients. In conclusion, β -thalassemia is characterized by pronounced iron overload and oxidative stress–related biochemical alterations. HAMP promoter variation

appears to contribute directly to iron dysregulation, while GSTP1 SNP may modulate oxidative stress response. These findings highlight the interplay between iron-regulatory and antioxidant genetic modifiers in disease heterogeneity.

Keywords:

β -thalassemia, iron overload, hepcidin, oxidative stress, single nucleotide polymorphism, ferritin.

Introduction

β -thalassemia is one of the most prevalent inherited hemoglobinopathies worldwide and remains a major clinical and public health concern, particularly in South Asia [1]. The disorder arises from mutations in the β -globin gene that impair β -globin chain synthesis, leading to chronic hemolytic anemia, ineffective erythropoiesis and in severe cases, lifelong transfusion dependence. Although advances in transfusion protocols and iron chelation therapy have improved survival, progressive iron overload remains a major determinant of morbidity and mortality due to its deleterious effects on hepatic, cardiac, and endocrine function [2]. Iron homeostasis in β -thalassemia is profoundly dysregulated. Under physiological conditions, systemic iron balance is tightly controlled by hepcidin, a hepatic peptide hormone that regulates iron export through its interaction with ferroportin. In β -thalassemia, ineffective erythropoiesis and chronic anemia suppress hepcidin expression despite systemic iron excess [3]. Elevated erythroid-derived signals further inhibit hepcidin synthesis, resulting in enhanced intestinal iron absorption and increased iron release from macrophages. This paradoxical suppression of hepcidin in the setting of iron overload accelerates iron accumulation, ultimately promoting oxidative tissue injury. Iron excess plays a central role in disease pathophysiology through the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) via Fenton chemistry [4]. Excess labile iron catalyzes hydroxyl radical formation, leading to lipid peroxidation, mitochondrial dysfunction,

DNA damage, and activation of inflammatory pathways. These mechanisms contribute to progressive hepatic injury, cardiomyopathy, endocrine dysfunction, and renal stress. However, considerable variability exists in the degree of iron loading and organ damage among patients with similar β -globin genotypes, suggesting that additional genetic modifiers may influence iron metabolism and antioxidant defense capacity [5].

Among potential modulators of iron regulation, variants in the Hemojuvencin Antimicrobial Peptide (HAMP) gene, which encodes hepcidin, are of particular interest. Promoter single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNP) such as rs10421768 (-582 A>G) may alter transcriptional activity and thereby influence hepcidin expression. Such variants could exacerbate iron accumulation in β -thalassemia by further impairing hepcidin-mediated control of ferroportin [6]. In parallel, genes involved in oxidative stress response may modulate susceptibility to iron-induced tissue damage. Glutathione S-Transferase Pi 1 (GSTP1), a phase II detoxification enzyme, plays a critical role in neutralizing ROS through glutathione conjugation [7]. The rs1695 (Ile105Val) SNP may alter catalytic efficiency and antioxidant capacity, potentially influencing individual vulnerability to oxidative injury in an iron-overloaded environment [8].

Although iron overloaded and oxidative stress are recognised as main culprit to β -thalassemia pathology, the interactive contribution of iron-regulatory and antioxidant gene variants to biochemical and clinical heterogeneity remains inadequately defined, particularly in South Asian populations [9]. Previous studies have largely evaluated these pathways in isolation, with limited efforts to integrate genetic polymorphisms and functional biochemical parameters within a unified analytical framework.

To address this gap, the present study systematically investigated hepatic and renal function indices, serum ferritin, and variation in HAMP (rs10421768) and GSTP1 (rs1695) in β -thalassemia patients and matched healthy controls. By integrating molecular and biochemical

profiling within the same cohort, this study seeks to delineate the interplay between iron dysregulation and oxidative stress related genetic modifiers, thereby identifying potential determinants of disease variability and markers relevant for risk stratification.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Participants

This case control study was conducted on 200 beta thalassemia major patients (diagnosed) visiting to the transfusion ward of Rajindra Government Medical College and Hospital, Patiala, Punjab, India. 200 healthy age matched individuals serve as control group. The study protocol was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee of the Punjabi University of Patiala (approval code no:2018/102).

Inclusion Exclusion Criteria

The beta thalassemia major patients, who were taking blood transfusion regularly followed by iron chelation therapy were included in the study, whereas person having alpha thalassemia and any other hemoglobinopathies were excluded from the study. The patients were assured that their information would remain confidential and informed consent was taken from them before the data.

Sample Collection and Processing

5 ml of peripheral blood were collected, 3 mL in plain vacutainers for serum and 2 mL in Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) vials for molecular analysis. Serum was separated by centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes and stored at -80°C . EDTA vial samples were stored at -20°C until DNA extraction.

Biochemical Analysis

Serum ferritin levels were quantified using Chemiluminescent Immunoassay (CLIA), a sensitive and fully automated method widely used in clinical diagnostics [10]. Serum creatinine was measured enzymatically using creatininase or creatinine deaminase, which catalyze its conversion into detectable products [11]. SGOT and SGPT activities were evaluated based on their transamination reactions, converting L-aspartate or L-alanine respectively with α -ketoglutarate into oxaloacetate or pyruvate and L-glutamate, with enzymatic detection of the products [12]. Serum urea was estimated colorimetrically through urease-mediated hydrolysis, where the liberated ammonia reacts with a chromogenic reagent to form a measurable-colored complex [13]. Collectively, these standardized biochemical assays provided reliable and sensitive quantification of key metabolic and liver function parameters in the study.

Molecular Analysis

DNA Extraction

Genomic DNA was isolated from EDTA blood using the phenol–chloroform method (Sambrook & Russell, 2006). DNA quality and quantity were assessed by agarose gel electrophoresis and spectrophotometry.

Genotyping of Selected SNPs

The study investigated two SNPs associated with iron regulation and oxidative stress using PCR-based techniques. The HAMP rs10421768 SNP was genotyped using ARMS-PCR [14] and GSTP1 rs1695 were analyzed through PCR-RFLP assays [15]. Amplified PCR products and the resulting restriction fragments were separated on agarose gels, and genotypes were determined by comparing the observed band patterns.

Primer Sequences and Genotyping Details

Table 1. Primers and Genotyping Conditions for Selected SNPs

Gene	SNP ID	Technique	Primer Sequence (5'-3')	Reference
HAMP	rs10421768	ARMS-PCR	Forward inner (G): GGTCTGACACTGGGAAAACAGCG Reverse inner (A): GTGTGCCCGATCCGCCCGT Forward outer: CTTAAGCGATCTGCCTCAG Reverse outer: AGGAGTGTCTGGCATGTTG	¹⁶
GSTP1	rs1695	PCR-RFLP	Forward: GTAGTTTGCCCAAGGTCAAG Reverse: AGCCACCTGAGGGGTAAG	¹⁷

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 26, and SNPStats software. Group comparisons were performed using t-tests. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Biochemical Markers Assessment

Hepatic Function Parameters

Liver enzyme profiling revealed significant alterations in β -thalassemia patients compared to healthy controls. SGOT levels were markedly elevated in the patient cohort, demonstrating considerable deviation from normal reference ranges (Figure-1A). Similarly, SGPT levels showed substantial elevation in β -thalassemia patients relative to controls, with statistically significant differences observed between the two groups ($p < 0.05$) (Figure-1B). These findings indicate compromised hepatic function in the disease population, likely reflecting chronic iron accumulation and oxidative stress in hepatocytes.

Figure 1: Comparison of biochemical parameters SGOT and SGPT between β -thalassemia patients and healthy controls.

Renal Function Parameters

Kidney function assessment through serum urea and creatinine measurements demonstrated significant impairment in β -thalassemia patients. Figure-2A revealed that urea was substantially elevated in the patient group compared to healthy controls, with statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$). Whereas creatinine was found elevated but showing the insignificant results (figure-2B). Elevated urea suggest progressive renal dysfunction in β -thalassemia patients, potentially attributable to iron-induced nephrotoxicity and chronic hemolysis-related complications.

Figure 2: Comparison of biochemical parameters between Urea and creatinine β -thalassemia patients and healthy controls.

Iron Metabolism Markers

In figure-3, Serum ferritin, a critical indicator of total body iron stores, showed dramatically elevated levels in β -thalassemia patients relative to controls ($p < 0.05$). This marked elevation reflects the pathological iron overload characteristic of β -thalassemia, resulting from transfusion-dependent anemia and enhanced intestinal iron absorption in the setting of chronic ineffective erythropoiesis.

Figure 3: Serum ferritin level comparison between β -thalassemia patients and healthy controls

Gene Single Nucleotide Polymorphism Associations

GSTP1 rs1695 SNP Analysis

The genotype distribution of GSTP1 rs1695 SNP was evaluated in β -thalassemia patients and healthy controls (Table 1). GSTP1 encodes a phase-2 detoxification enzyme involved in glutathione-mediated antioxidant defense and is functionally relevant to oxidative stress regulation rather than the primary genetic basis of β -thalassemia.

Under the codominant model, using the G/G genotype as the reference category, the A/G genotype showed a statistically significant difference in distribution between cases and controls (OR: 1.69; $p < 0.0001$), whereas the A/A genotype also demonstrated a significant difference (OR: 0.26). These findings indicate variation in genotype frequencies between the two groups.

In the dominant model (A/G-A/A vs G/G), no statistically significant difference was observed (OR: 1.42; $p = 0.21$), suggesting that the presence of at least one A allele does not significantly alter genotype distribution relative to the G/G genotype.

However, the recessive model (A/A vs G/G-A/G) revealed a highly significant difference (OR: 0.17; $p < 0.0001$), indicating that individuals homozygous for the A allele differ significantly from carriers of the G allele. Similarly, the over-dominant model (A/G vs G/G-A/A) showed strong statistical significance (Or: 2.59; $p=0.0001$), reflecting a distinct distribution of the heterozygous genotype compared to the combined homozygous genotypes.

At the allelic level, the A allele frequency was 51% in cases and 55% in controls, while the G allele frequency was 49% in cases and 45% in controls. This difference was not statistically significant (OR: 0.72; $p=0.1$), indicating comparable overall allele distribution between groups.

Overall, genotype-based analysis revealed statistically significant differences under certain inheritance models, while allele frequencies did not differ significantly. These findings

describe variation in GSTP1 rs1695 genotype distribution between β -thalassemia patients and controls, which may be affect the oxidative stress handling due to iron overloading.

Table 1: Association Analysis of GSTP1 rs1695 SNP with Oxidative Stress in β -Thalassemia Risk Under Different Genetic Models

Models GSTP1 rs1695	Genotype	β -thalassemia Case n(%)	Control n(%)	OR (95%)	p- value
Codominant	G/G	35(17.5)	26(13)	Ref	
	A/G	134(67)	168(84)	1.69 (0.97-2.94)	<0.0001*
	A/A	31(15.5)	6(3)	0.26 (0.09-0.72)	
Dominant	G/G	35(17.5)	26(13)	Ref	0.21
	A/G-A/A	165(82.5)	174(87)	1.42 (0.82-2.46)	
Recessive	G/G-A/G	169(84.5)	194(97)	Ref	<0.0001*
	A/A	31(15.5)	6(3)	0.17 (0.007-0.41)	
Over-dominant	G/G-A/A	66(33)	32(16)	Ref	0.0001*
	A/G	134(67)	168(84)	2.59 (1.60-4.18)	
Allele	Cases n (%)	Controls n (%)	OR (95% CI)	p-value	
A	204 (51.0)	220 (55)	Ref.	0.1	
G	196(49.0)	180 (45)	0.72(0.48-1.07)		

Association between GSTP1 rs1695 genotypes and β -thalassemia susceptibility analyzed using codominant, dominant, recessive, over-dominant, and allele-based genetic models. Odds ratios (OR), 95% confidence intervals (CI), and p-values were calculated to estimate the strength of association. Statistically significant results are indicated by $p < 0.05$.

HAMP rs10421786 SNP Analysis

The HAMP rs10421786 SNP showed distinct patterns of association with β -thalassemia under various genetic models (Table 2). In the codominant model, individuals carrying the A/G genotype demonstrated significantly different odds of disease compared to the A/A genotype (OR: 0.15), while the G/G genotype showed an even stronger association (OR: 0.07). These findings indicate that both heterozygous and homozygous G genotypes differ markedly from the A/A genotype in relation to disease status.

In the dominant model, a highly significant association was observed (OR: 0.12; $p < 0.0001$), suggesting that individuals carrying at least one G allele (A/G or G/G) differ significantly from those with the A/A genotype. Similarly, the recessive model showed a significant association for the G/G genotype (OR: 0.21; $p = 0.0002$), indicating that individuals with two copies of the G allele exhibit a distinct disease distribution compared to the combined A/A and A/G genotypes.

The over-dominant model also revealed prominent statistical significance (OR: 0.43; $p = 0.00007$), suggesting that the heterozygous A/G genotype differs significantly from the combined homozygous groups.

At the allele level, the frequency of the A allele was lower in cases (40%) compared to controls (75%), whereas the G allele was more frequent in cases (60%) than controls (25%). This difference was highly significant (OR: 0.24; $p = 0.0001$), indicating a substantial variation in allele distribution between β -thalassemia patients and healthy controls.

Considering all findings of this study, the HAMP rs10421786 SNP describe convincing and consistent associations with β -thalassemia across all genetic models evaluated.

Table 2: Association Analysis of HAMP rs10421786 SNP with Iron Overloading in β -Thalassemia Risk Under Different Genetic Models

Models HAMP rs10421786	Genotype	β -thalassemia Case n(%)	Control n(%)	OR (95%)	p- value
Codominant	A/A	30(15)	120(60)	Ref	-
	A/G	100(50)	60(30)	0.15 (0.09-0.25)	<0.0001*
	G/G	70(35)	20(10)	0.07 (0.04-0.14)	-
Dominant	A/A	30(15)	120(60)	Ref	<0.0001*
	A/G-G/G	170(85)	80(40)	0.12 (0.07-0.19)	
Recessive	A/A-A/G	130(65)	180(90)	Ref	

	G/G	70(35)	20 (10%)	0.21 (0.12-0.36)	0.0002*
Over-dominant	A/A-G/G	100(50)	140(70%)	Ref	0.00007*
	A/G	100(50)	60(30%)	0.43 (0.28-0.65)	
Allele	Cases n (%)	Controls n (%)	OR (95% CI)	p-value	
A	160 (40)	300 (75)	Ref.		
G	240 (60)	100 (25)	0.24 (0.18-0.34)	0.0001*	

Association between HAMP rs10421786 genotypes and susceptibility to β -thalassemia was evaluated using codominant, dominant, recessive, over-dominant, and allele comparison models. Odds ratios (ORs), 95% confidence intervals (95% CI), and p-values were calculated to estimate risk. Statistically significant associations are indicated as $p < 0.05$.

Discussion

The present study demonstrates a compelling interaction between biochemical disturbances and genetic single nucleotide polymorphism in shaping the pathophysiological landscape of β -thalassemia. The biochemical alterations observed in this cohort reflect systemic iron dysregulation and organ involvement, while the genetic findings suggest that variants in iron-regulatory and antioxidant pathways may modulate individual susceptibility to disease severity.

The marked elevation of liver enzymes (SGOT and SGPT), together with considerable ferritin accumulation, reflects the integrated consequences of chronic iron overload and its associated oxidative burden [18]. However, these biochemical abnormalities were not uniformly expressed among patients, suggesting that underlying genetic variability may profoundly influence disease expression.

Variation in GSTP1 rs1695 SNP appear to contribute to differences in oxidative stress management. GSTP1 encodes a key phase II detoxification enzyme involved in glutathione conjugation and the neutralization of reactive oxygen species. Individuals carrying the A/A genotype may possess relatively increased antioxidant capacity, enabling more efficient detoxification of iron induced oxidative metabolites [19]. Although this SNP does not directly

regulate iron accumulation, it may modulate the extent of hepatocellular injury resulting from oxidative stress. Such a mechanism could partially explain the inter-individual variability observed in liver enzyme levels among β -thalassemia patients, indicating that GSTP1 functions as a modifier of tissue damage rather than a primary determinant of iron overload [20].

In contrast, the HAMP rs10421786 SNP appears to exert influence at a more fundamental regulatory level. Heparin is the central hormone governing systemic iron homeostasis, controlling intestinal iron absorption and macrophage iron release. Genetic variation within HAMP may therefore alter iron absorption efficiency and tissue iron deposition patterns [21]. Individuals carrying the G allele demonstrated a markedly different genotype distribution compared to controls, suggesting that alterations in heparin-mediated regulation substantially affect disease susceptibility. Enhanced or more balanced iron regulation associated with specific HAMP genotypes may limit excessive tissue iron loading, thereby reducing downstream hepatic and renal stress [22]. This mechanistic framework aligns with the observed differences in ferritin levels and organ function markers.

Renal parameters, including elevated urea and modest changes in creatinine, further support the concept that iron-mediated toxicity extends beyond hepatic injury [23]. Variability in these biochemical indices may reflect differential genetic capacity for iron handling and oxidative stress management. While HAMP SNP likely influence the magnitude of iron burden, GSTP1 variants may determine the efficiency with which oxidative injury is neutralized once iron accumulation has occurred [24]. Thus, the two genes appear to act at distinct yet complementary levels within the disease pathway: HAMP primarily influencing iron regulation, and GSTP1 modulating cellular resilience to oxidative damage [25].

An interesting observation emerges when comparing the distribution patterns of these SNPs. The HAMP G allele demonstrates a distribution consistent with a direct role in disease

susceptibility, suggesting that iron regulatory efficiency significantly influences the likelihood of pathological progression [26]. Conversely, GSTP1 genotype distribution suggests a more complex role, potentially modifying disease severity or biochemical phenotype rather than acting as a primary susceptibility factor [27]. This distinction underscores the multifactorial nature of β -thalassemia pathophysiology, wherein iron dysregulation initiates tissue injury and antioxidant defense capacity modulates its extent.

Conclusion

Collectively, these findings reinforce the concept that β -thalassemia extends beyond a defect in hemoglobin synthesis and represents a disorder profoundly shaped by iron metabolism, oxidative stress, and host genetic background [28]. Genetic polymorphisms within iron-regulatory and antioxidant pathways significantly influence biochemical expression and may account for inter-individual variability in organ involvement. Recognition of these genetic modifiers provides a stronger mechanistic understanding of disease heterogeneity and may ultimately support more individualized therapeutic strategies targeting iron chelation and oxidative stress management.

Conflict of interest: There is no conflict of interest.

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